

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

2026-YIL

IYUN/6-SON, III-QISM

ISSN: 2992-8982

<https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz/>

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Bosh muharrir:

Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich

*Elektron nashr. 2026-yil, iyun.
III-qism*

Bosh muharrir o'rinbosari:

Karimov Norboy G'aniyevich

Muharrir:

Qurbonov Sherzod Ismatillayevich

Tahrir hay'ati:

Salimov Oqil Umrzoqov vch, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Abduraxmanov Kalandar Xodjayev vch, O'zbekiston Fanlar akademiyasi akademigi
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Rae Kvon Chung, Janubiy Koreya, TDIU faxriy professori, "Nobel" mukofoti laureati
Osman Mesten, Turkiya parlamenti a'zosi, Turkiya – O'zbekiston do'stlik jamiyati rahbari
Axmedov Durbek Kudratillayev vch, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Abduraxmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Kalonov Muxiddin Baxritdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Siddiqova Sadoqat G'afforovna, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Xudoyqulov Sadirdin Karimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Maxmudov Nosir, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Samadov Asqarjon Nishonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, professor
Slizovskiy Dimitriy Yegorovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyev vch, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Axmedov Ikrom Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abdug'aniyev vch, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xajiyev Baxtiyor Dushaboyev vch, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Hakimov Nazar Hakimovich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Musayeva Shoirazimovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), professor
Ali Konak (Ali Ko'nak), iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor (Turkiya)
Cham Tat Huei, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD), professor (Malayziya)
Foziljonov Ibrohimjon Sotvoldix'ja o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dots.
Faxridinov Zafarjon Faxridin o'g'li, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi HIJQKD boshqarma boshlig'i
Utayev Uktam Choriyev vch, Anijon viloyati prokurorining o'rinbosari
Ochilov Farkhod, O'zb. Res. Bosh prokuraturasi IJQK Departamentining Namangan viloyati boshqarmasi boshlig'i
Buzrukxonov Sarvarxon Munavvarxonovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Axmedov Javohir Jamolovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Toxirov Jaloliddin Ochil o'g'li, texnika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), katta o'qituvchi
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), v.b. dots.
Djudi Smetana, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Krissi Lyuis, pedagogika fanlari nomzodi, dotsent (AQSH)
Glazova Marina Viktorovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (Moskva)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, falsafa fanlari doktori (PhD) (Turkiya)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon o'g'li, TDIU ITI departamenti rahbari
Ochilov Bobur Baxtiyor o'g'li, TDIU katta o'qituvchisi
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamxonovna, bank-moliya akademiyasi professori, DSc., professor.
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Editorial board:

Salimov Okil Umrzokovich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Abdurakhmanov Kalandar Khodjavevich, Academician of the Academy of Sciences of Uzbekistan
Sharipov Kongiratbay Avezimbetovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Rae Kwon Chung, South Korea, Honorary Professor at TSUE, Nobel Prize Laureate
Osman Mesten, Member of the Turkish Parliament, Head of the Turkey–Uzbekistan Friendship Society
Akhmedov Durbek Kudratillayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Sayfullo Normatovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Abdurakhmanova Gulnora Kalandarovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Kalonov Mukhiddin Bakhridinovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Siddikova Sadokat Gafforovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogical Sciences
Khudoykulov Sadirdin Karimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Makhmudov Nosir, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Yuldashev Mutallib Ibragimovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Samadov Askarjon Nishonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor
Slizovskiy Dmitriy Yegorovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Mustafakulov Sherzod Igamberdiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Akhmedov Ikrom Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Eshtayev Alisher Abduganiyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khajiyev Bakhtiyor Dushaboyevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khakimov Nazar Khakimovich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Musayeva Shoira Azimovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Professor
Ali Konak, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor (Turkey)
Cham Tat Huei, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD), Professor (Malaysia)
Foziljonov Ibrokhimjon Sotvoldikhoja ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Fakhridinov Zafarjon Fakhridin ogli, Head of the DCEC under the Prosecutor General's Office of the Rep. of Uzb.
Utayev Uktam Choriyevich, Deputy Prosecutor of Anijan Region
Ochilov Farkhod, Head of the Namangan Regional Department of the Department of Internal Affairs of Rep. of Uzb.
Buzrukkhonov Sarvarkhon Munavvarkhonovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Akhmedov Javokhir Jamolovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences
Tokhirov Jaloliddin Ochil ugli, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Technical Sciences, Senior Lecturer
Bobobekov Ergash Abdumalikovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Acting Associate Professor
Judi Smetana, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Chrissy Lewis, Candidate of Pedagogical Sciences, Associate Professor (USA)
Glazova Marina Victorovna, Doctor of Sciences in Economics (Moscow)
Nosirova Nargiza Jamoliddin kizi, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Sevil Piriyeva Karaman, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) (Turkey)
Mirzaliyev Sanjar Makhamatjon ugli, Head of the Department of Scientific Research and Innovations, TSUE
Ochilov Bobur Bakhtiyor ugli, Senior lecturer at TSUI
Golisheva Yelena Vyacheslavovna, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor.
Abdukarimova Dinara Rustamkhanovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Ikramov Murod Akramovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Nazarova Ra'no Rustamovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor

Ekspertlar kengashi:

Berkinov Bazarbay, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Po'latov Baxtiyor Alimovich, texnika fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, falsafa fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), professor
Xalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, iqtisodiyot fanlari nomzodi, dotsent
Hakimov Ziyodulla Ahmadovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
G'afurov Doniyor Orifovich, pedagogika fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD)
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Tuxtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, iqtisodiyot fanlari bo'yicha falsafa doktori (PhD), dotsent
Xamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarim qizi, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori, dotsent
Yaxshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, katta o'qituvchi
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, mustaqil tadqiqotchi
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Geografiya fanlari doktori, professori
Umirzoqov Ja'sur Artiqboy o'g'li, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent
Zebo Kuldasheva, iqtisodiyot fanlari doktori (DSc), dotsent

Board of Experts:

Berkinov Bazarbay, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Pulatov Bakhtiyor Alimovich, Doctor of Technical Sciences (DSc), Professor
Aliyev Bekdavlal Aliyevich, Doctor of Philosophy (DSc), Professor
Isakov Janabay Yakubbayevich, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Professor
Khalikov Suyun Ravshanovich, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Rustamov Ilhomiddin, Candidate of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Khakimov Ziyodulla Akhmadovich, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Kamilova Iroda Xusniddinovna, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics
Gafurov Doniyor Orifovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Pedagogy
Fayziyev Oybek Raximovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Tukhtabayev Jamshid Sharafetdinovich, Doctor of Philosophy (PhD) in Economics, Associate Professor
Khamidova Faridaxon Abdulkarimovna, Doctor of Economic Sciences, Associate Professor
Yakhshiboyeva Laylo Abdisattorovna, Senior Lecturer
Babayeva Zuhra Yuldashevna, Independent Researcher
Komilova Nilufar Karshiboyevna, Doctor of Geographical Sciences, Professor
Umirzokov Jasur Artiqboy ugli, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor
Zebo Kuldasheva, Doctor of Economic Sciences (DSc), Associate Professor

- 08.00.01 Iqtisodiyot nazariyasi
- 08.00.02 Makroiqtisodiyot
- 08.00.03 Sanoat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.04 Qishloq xo'jaligi iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.05 Xizmat ko'rsatish tarmoqlari iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.06 Ekonometrika va statistika
- 08.00.07 Moliya, pul muomalasi va kredit
- 08.00.08 Buxgalteriya hisobi, iqtisodiy tahlil va audit
- 08.00.09 Jahon iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.10 Demografiya. Mehnat iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.11 Marketing
- 08.00.12 Mintaqaviy iqtisodiyot
- 08.00.13 Menejment
- 08.00.14 Iqtisodiyotda axborot tizimlari va texnologiyalari
- 08.00.15 Tadbirkorlik va kichik biznes iqtisodiyoti
- 08.00.16 Raqamli iqtisodiyot va xalqaro raqamli integratsiya
- 08.00.17 Turizm va mehmonxona faoliyati

Muassis: "Ma'rifat-print-media" MChJ

Hamkorlarimiz: Toshkent davlat iqtisodiyot universiteti,
O'zbekiston Respublikasi Bosh prokuraturasi huzuridagi Iqtisodiy
jinoyatlarga qarshi kurashish departamenti

Jurnalning ilmiyligi:

“Yashil” iqtisodiyot va
taraqqiyot” jurnali

O'zbekiston Respublikasi
Oliy ta'lim, fan va innovatsiyalar
vazirligi huzuridagi Oliy
attestatsiya komissiyasi
rayosatining
2023-yil 1-apreldagi
336/3-sonli qarori bilan
ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

MUNDARIJA

SUD BOSHQARUVCHILARI FAOLIYATINING IQTISODIY RAG'BATLANTIRISH TIZIMI VA ULARNING SUBSIDIAR JAVOBGARLIGI: MUAMMOLAR VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	12
Soliyev Damirjon Nurmatovich	
BLOKCHEYN TEKNOLOGIYASI ASOSIDA MOLIVAVIY TRANZAKSIYALARNI NAZORAT QILISH TIZIMI (SMART-KONTRAKTLAR, MARKAZLASHMAGAN MA'LUMOTLAR BAZASI VA AUDIT IZLARI)	18
Olimova Mukhlisa Vohidjon qizi	
SANOAT SEKTORIDA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH: STRATEGIK AFZALLIKLAR VA TO'SIQLAR TAHLILI	26
Xatamov Ochildi Qurbonovich	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ БАНКОВСКОЙ СИСТЕМЫ УЗБЕКИСТАНА КАК ФАКТОР ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЕЁ КОНКУРЕНТОСПОСОБНОСТИ	32
PhD. Юлдашева С.Ш	
TREND MODELLARI YORDAMIDA MEHNAT RESURSLARI SONINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH	38
Haydarova Dinora Atamurot qizi	
МЕТОДОЛОГИЧЕСКИЕ ОСНОВЫ ВЫКУПА И ПРОДАЖИ КВОТ НА ОРОСИТЕЛЬНУЮ ВОДУ	43
Гоженко Борис Владимирович	
MOLIVAVIY LEVERIJ SAMARASI VA QARZ MABLAG'LARINI BOSHQARISHDA UNDA FOYDALANISH	50
Latipova Shaxnoza Maxmudovna	
XIZMATLAR SOHASIDA WEBMONEY TO'LOV TIZIMINI KOMPYUTERDA O'RNATISH VA SOZLASHNING IQTISODIYOTDAGI ROLI	55
Fazilat Esirgapovna Jomonqulova	
Nizomov Murod	
Qurbonboyeva Rayhon Bahronjon qizi	
MECHANISMS FOR THE FORMATION AND DEVELOPMENT OF A HEALTHY LIFESTYLE	58
Shukhrat Mashrabboevich Mamadaliyev	
BANK SEKTORIDA OPERATSION SAMARADORLIK VA XAVFLARNI BOSHQARISHNI BAHOLASH	62
R.I.Rashidov	
A.N. Elmurodov	
A.A. Muhiddinov	
TRANSFORMING ECONOMIC GOVERNANCE IN UZBEKISTAN THROUGH DIGITAL PUBLIC SECTOR TOOLS	68
Bokhodirov Boriykhon Boburovich	
Bahromjon Urmanov	
TIJORAT BANKLARINING INVESTITSIYA VA KREDIT SALOHİYATINI BOSHQARISH	74
Ergashova Nilufar Sobirovna	
DEHQON XO'JALIKLARIDA QO'SHILGAN QIYMAT ZANJIRINING SHAKLLANISHI VA UNGA TA'SIR ETUVCHI OMILLAR	80
Azizov Shohsuvor Yuldashevich	
VERTIKAL INTEGRATSIYALASHGAN BANK TUZILMASINI "YAGONA MFO" TEKNOLOGIYASI ASOSIDA TRANSFORMATSIYA QILISH SXEMASI	84
Qo'shboqov Doniyorbek Maxramqulovich	

O'ZBEKISTON SANOAT KORXONALARIDA "YASHIL EKOTIZIM" VA RESURS SAMARADORLIGI (RECP)NI JORIY ETISHNING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARI HAMDA EMISSIALARNI KAMAYTIRISH SAMARADORLIGI.....	90
Do'stqobilov Ulug'bek Ibrohimovich	
TURIZM SOHASIDA OILAVIY TADBIRKORLIK TUSHUNCHALARINING MAZMUN VA MOHIYATIGA ILMIY-NAZARIY YONDASHUVLAR	94
Pardayeva Ozoda Mamayunusovna	
СНИЖЕНИЕ ТЕХНИЧЕСКИХ И КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ ПОТЕРЬ ЭЛЕКТРОЭНЕРГИИ КАК НАПРАВЛЕНИЕ ПОВЫШЕНИЯ ЭКОНОМИЧЕСКОЙ ЭФФЕКТИВНОСТИ РАСПРЕДЕЛИТЕЛЬНЫХ СЕТЕЙ УЗБЕКИСТАНА	100
Маърупова Дилсора Абдулла кизи	
O'ZBEKISTON QURILISH SOHASIDA RAQAMLI TRANSFORMATSIYA VA YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISHNING INSTITUTIONAL SHART-SHAROITLARI.....	105
Qodirov Sardorbek Isroiljon o'g'li	
АКАДЕМИЧЕСКИЕ НАВЫКИ И ОСОБЕННОСТИ ИХ ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ	113
Усманова Зумрад Исламовна	
Рахматуллаев Алижон	
Сайфитдинов Азизжон	
G'AZNACHILIK OPERATSIYALARINING BANKLIKVIDLIGINI TA'MINLASHDAGI O'RNI (SILICON VALLEY BANK MISOLIDA).....	119
Axadov Shahboz Shuxrat o'g'li	
ТРАНСФОРМАЦИЯ СИСТЕМЫ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ТВЁРДЫМИ БЫТОВЫМИ ОТХОДАМИ В Г. ТАШКЕНТЕ: ОТ ПОЛИГОННОГО ЗАХОРОНЕНИЯ К РЕСУРСНО-ЭНЕРГЕТИЧЕСКОМУ ИСПОЛЬЗОВАНИЮ	127
Джусупов Кубанычбек	
STRATEGIK BOSHQARUV HISOBI AXBOROT TA'MINOTINING METODOLOGIK ASOSLARINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	133
Umidjon Kostayev	
DEVELOPMENT OF A METHODOLOGY FOR TEACHING STUDENTS OBJECTORIENTED PROGRAMMING IN A VIRTUAL COLLABORATIVE ENVIRONMENT USING GENERATIVE ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS	140
Saidova Dilfuza Ergashovna	
AUDIT SIFATI NAZORATINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH	145
Muydinov Erkin Jamaldinovich	
THE ROLE OF E-COMMERCE IN ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT: EVIDENCE FROM UZBEKISTAN'S DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION.....	152
Shakhriddinova Sitora Tolibjon kizi	
THE IMPACT OF SUSTAINABILITY PRACTICES IN THE AGRICULTURAL INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN.....	157
Yorkin Ziyodullaev	
Munisa Bekmirzaeva	
РОЛЬ ЦИРКУЛЯРНОЙ ЭКОНОМИКИ В ЗЕЛЕНОМ РОСТЕ В УЗБЕКИСТАНЕ.....	166
Мохамед Эйд Али Балбаа	
Усманова Азиза Алишеровна	
OZIQ-OVQAT SANOATI KORXONALARIDA SAMARADORLIKNI OSHIRISHNING INNOVATSION YO'LLARI.....	173
Shakirxodjaeva Zuxraxon Rustamxanovna	
BARQAROR RIVOJLANISH HISOBOTLARINI TUZISH MASALALARI: XALQARO TAJRIBA VA TAKOMILLASHTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI.....	180
Menglikulov Baxtiyor Yusupovich	

THE IMPACT OF SUSTAINABILITY PRACTICES IN THE AGRICULTURAL INDUSTRY IN UZBEKISTAN	184
Yorkin Ziyodullaev	
Munisa Bekmirzaeva	
TASTE OF PLACE: HOW LOCAL-INGREDIENT SOURCING AFFECTS GUEST SATISFACTION AND MENU PROFITABILITY IN HOTEL RESTAURANTS	193
Bahodirova Durdona	
Atametova Sevara	
INTERACTIONS IN CREATIVE TOURISM: RESIDENTS' PERSPECTIVES IN UZBEKISTAN.....	198
Dildora Khodjaeva Mukhamedkhodjaevna	
Jasmin Raxmidinova	
XO'JALIK YURITUVCHISUBYEKTLARNING LIKVIDLILIGINI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI	204
Bauyetdinov M.J.	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTGA O'TISH SHAROITIDA MINTAQA TABIIY RESURSLARIDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARI (BUXORO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	212
Safarov Otabek Abduhamidovich	
SANOAT KORXONALARIDA INNOVATSION FAOLIYAT SAMARADORLIGINING NAZARIY JIHATLARI	218
O'rinov Akmaljon Axmadjonovich	
ТЕОРИИ УПРАВЛЕНИЯ ФИНАНСОВЫМИ РИСКАМИ В БАНКОВСКОЙ ДЕЯТЕЛЬНОСТИ.....	223
Убайдуллаева Мафтунахон Акмалхон кизи	
SURXONDARYO VILOYATI IQTISODIYOTIGA JALB ETILAYOTGAN INVESTITSİYALAR SAMARADORLIGI TAHLILI	230
Xatamova Manzura Ochildiyevna	
TURISTIK MAHSULOT MARKETINGI: NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA RIVOJLANTIRISH YO'NALISHLARI	240
Usmanova Zumrad Islamovna	
IN VITRO TEXNOLOGIYASI ASOSIDA KARTOSHKA URUG'CHILIGI ZANJIRI SAMARADORLIGINI IQTISODIY BAHOLASHNING NAZARIY ASOSLARI	244
Mardonova Zarifa Numonjonovna	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT OPERATSIYALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH UCHUN RESURSLAR YETARLILIGINI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI	251
Sheraliyev Olimjon O'ktam o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA ESG MOLIYALASHTIRISH TIZIMINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISHNING USTUVOR YO'NALISHLARI VA MEXANIZMLARI	258
Ajibayeva Raiya Maxsutovna	
YASHIL MOLIYALASHTIRISH INSTRUMENTLARI ORQALI BARQAROR IQTISODIY O'SISHNI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI	262
Ajibayeva Raiya Maxsutovna	
ANIQ FANLARNI O'QITISHDA METAKOGNITIV YONDASHUVLAR: TEORETIK ASOSLAR, KOGNITIV ARHITEKTURA VA AMALIY TRANSFER MUAMMOLARI	265
Namozov Diyorbek Baxtiyor o'g'li	
XUFYONA IQTISODIYOTNING MOHIYATI VA UNI O'ZBEKISTONDA KAMAYTIRISH CHORA-TADBIRLARI	270
Kalandarov R.A.	
RAQAMLI TO'LOV TIZIMLARIDA ALOQA OPERATORLARI ROLINI OSHIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	276
Nuraliyev Nurbek Rustam o'g'li	
DAVLAT BUDJETI DAROMADLARI BARQARORLIGINI TA'MINLASHDA BILVOSITA SOLIQQA TORTISHNING ASOSIY YO'NALISHLARI	281
Mansurova Arofatxon Shavkat qizi	

INTERNATIONAL TRENDS AND THE LEGAL FRAMEWORK OF E-COMMERCE DEVELOPMENT IN UZBEKISTAN.....	286
Usmanova Zumrad Islamovna	
ISSUES OF ACCOUNTING RECOGNITION AND VALUATION OF LONG-TERM ASSETS UNDER INTERNATIONAL FINANCIAL REPORTING STANDARDS (IFRS).....	290
Golib D. Tashmanov	
Ismandiyor B. Umirzokov	
СПЕЦИФИКА ФОРМИРОВАНИЯ РИСКОВ В СФЕРЕ ИНВЕСТИЦИОННЫХ ПЛАТФОРМ	297
Алиева Сусанна Сейрановна	
ZAMONAVIY AXBOROTLASHGAN TA'LIM MUHITIDA ANIQ FANLARNI O'QITISHNING KOGNITIV VA METAKOGNITIV DETERMINANTLARI.....	304
Shogeldieva Sabrina Omongeldiyevna	
BANKLARARO LIKVIDLILIKNI BOSHQARISHDA SUN'IY INTELLEKT VA BIG DATA TEXNOLOGIYALARINI QO'LLASH ISTIQBOLLARI	309
Baxromov Nodirjon Muxammadamin o'g'li	
OTMLARDA ILMIY-TEXNIK MAHSULOTLARNI TIJORATLASHTIRISHDA ISHTIROK ETADIGAN SUBYEKTLAR: ROLLAR, FUNKSIYALAR VA O'ZARO MUNOSABATLAR TAHLILI	313
Safarov Bekzod Istamovich	
TO'QIMACHILIK MAHSULOTLARI EKSPORTINI YASHIL MARKETING VOSITALARI ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH MEKANIZMI	319
Jo'raboyev Jurabek Muhibillo o'g'li	
O'ZBEKISTONDA AGROTURIZMNI RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI	323
Aktamov Olimjon Abdug'ani o'g'li	
SAVDO FAOLIYATIDA MIJOZ EHTIYOJLARINI ANIQLASH MEKANIZMLARI.....	333
Mamatraimov Islom Mamanazarovich	
TIJORAT BANKLARIDA KREDIT OPERATSIYALARI SAMARADORLIGINI OSHIRISH UCHUN RESURLAR YETARLILIGINI TA'MINLASH MASALALARI	338
Sheraliyev Olimjon O'ktam o'g'li	
ОСОБЕННОСТИ ФИНАНСИРОВАНИЯ СИСТЕМ ЗДРАВООХРАНЕНИЯ В СТРАНАХ ЕВРОПЕЙСКОГО СОЮЗА	345
Омокеев Максымбек Конколойевич	
O'ZBEKISTONDA YASHIL TADBIRKORLIK SUBYEKTLARINI MOLIYALASHTIRISH IMKONIYATLARI.....	351
Nurmetova Muyassar Jumanazarovna	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOT SHAROITIDA TOG' TURIZMINI BARQAROR RIVOJLANTIRISH ISTIQBOLLARI.....	358
Alimov Abdvakil Komil o'g'li	
TURIZMNI MINTAQAVIY RIVOJLANTIRISHDA DIVERSIFIKATSIYA JARAYONLARINING NAZARIY ASOSLARI VA HUDUDIY XUSUSIYATLARI.....	365
Abduxamidov Sarvar Adxamovich	
KICHIK BIZNESNI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING OBYEKTIV ZARURATI, TASHKILY-IQTISODIY JIHLTLARI.....	371
Nematjonova Risolatxon Dilshodbek qizi	
MINTAQQA IQTISODIYOTINI RIVOJLANTIRISHDA TIBBIY TURIZM RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGINI OSHIRISH OMILLARI	376
Yusupova Mehribon O'ktamovna	
SANOAT TARMOQLARIDA INVESTITSIYALARDAN SAMARALI FOYDALANISH YO'LLARINI EKONOMETRIK MODELLASHTIRISH (SURXONDARYO VILOYATI MISOLIDA)	381
Choriyev Tolib A'zamovich	
YASHIL IQTISODIYOTNING O'ZBEKISTON EKSPORT RAQOBATBARDOSHLIGIGA TA'SIRI: IMKONIYATLAR VA CBAM BILAN BOG'LIQ CHAQIRIQLAR	388
Djurayeva Rano Abdullayevna	
To'xliyeva Gulrux Dovron qizi	

AKSIYADORLIK JAMIYATLARIDA ASOSIY VOSITALAR HISOBINI TAKOMILLASHTIRISH.....	395
Avlayeva Oybarchin Olim qizi	
O‘ZBEKISTON TIJORAT BANKLARI KREDITLARINING BARQAROR O‘SISHINI TA‘MINLASH MASALALARI.....	400
Xasan Axmedov	
УЛУЧШЕНИЕ ОПЕРАЦИЙ С ЦЕННЫМИ БУМАГАМИ В КОММЕРЧЕСКИХ БАНКАХ	405
Ниёзов Зухур	
Набиев Достонбек	
RAQAMLI PLATFORMALAR ASOSIDA TURIZM XIZMATLARINI RIVOJLANTIRISHNING INNOVATSION MEXANIZMLARI.....	410
Davlatova Zamira Rajabboyevna	
DIGITAL TRANSFORMATION OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE: NEOLOGISMS, CODE SWITCHING AND THE PROBLEM OF LANGUAGE RESOURCES IN ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE TOOLS.....	415
Dilnoza Yuldasheva Bekmurodovna	
KICHIK KORXONALARDA BUXGALTERIYA HISOBI VA TAHLIL USLUBLARINI MILLIY STANDARTLAR ASOSIDA RIVOJLANTIRISH	420
Ochilov Shavkat Toshmamatovich	
Nurmetov Suhrobbek Bahrombek o‘g‘li	
INTERNAL AND EXTERNAL FACTORS IN THE FORMATION OF UZBEK TERMINOLOGY: HISTORICAL STAGES AND CURRENT STATE	424
Dilnoza Yuldasheva Bekmurodovna	
PRAGMATIC AND DERIVATIONAL CHANGES OF THE UZBEK LANGUAGE IN YOUTH SPEECH (BASED ON SOCIAL MEDIA AND MEDIA TEXTS)	429
Dilnoza Yuldasheva Bekmurodovna	
THE VOLUME OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION IN THE REGION AND THE ROLE OF REGIONAL SPECIALIZATION IN ENSURING FOOD SECURITY.....	434
Nurali Xolmatovich Bekmurodov	

THE VOLUME OF AGRICULTURAL PRODUCTION IN THE REGION AND THE ROLE OF REGIONAL SPECIALIZATION IN ENSURING FOOD SECURITY

Nurali Xolmatovich Bekmurodov

Candidate of Economic Sciences, Professor, Department of Economics
University of Business and Science
Tashkent, Uzbekistan

Abstract. This article analyzes the volume, structure, and role of agricultural production in ensuring food security through regional specialization. Using the FAO methodology and 2023 statistical data, the study identifies key indicators of food security and highlights the importance of balanced food consumption and sufficient food reserves. The results reveal distinct patterns of regional specialization: the Fergana Valley specializes in vegetable and fruit production, while the southern regions demonstrate strong potential in livestock and forage production. Correlation ($r = 0.78$) and regression ($R^2 = 0.61$) analyses confirm a strong positive relationship between infrastructure development and food security. The findings indicate that further improvement of storage facilities, logistics systems, and agricultural infrastructure can significantly strengthen regional food security and support sustainable agricultural development.

Keywords: Food security, regional specialization, agricultural production, infrastructure, Uzbekistan.

Annotatsiya. Mazkur maqolada hududlarda qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarish hajmi, tarkibi hamda hududiy ixtisoslashuvning oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini ta'minlashdagi o'rni tahlil qilingan. Tadqiqotda FAO metodologiyasi va 2023-yil statistik ma'lumotlaridan foydalanilgan. Natijalar oziq-ovqat xavfsizligining muhim ko'rsatkichlarini aniqlash hamda hududiy ixtisoslashuvning samaradorligini baholash imkonini berdi. Tahlillar Farg'ona vodiysi hududlari meva-sabzavotchilik mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarishga, janubiy hududlar esa chorvachilik va yem-xashak yetishtirishga ixtisoslashganligini ko'rsatdi. Korrelyatsion ($r = 0,78$) va regressiya ($R^2 = 0,61$) tahlillari infratuzilma rivojlanishi bilan oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi o'rtasida kuchli ijobiy bog'liqlik mavjudligini tasdiqladi. Tadqiqot natijalari saqlash tizimlari, logistika va qishloq xo'jaligi infratuzilmasini yanada takomillashtirish hududiy oziq-ovqat xavfsizligini mustahkamlash hamda tarmoqning barqaror rivojlanishini ta'minlashga xizmat qilishini ko'rsatadi.

Kalit so'zlar: oziq-ovqat xavfsizligi, hududiy ixtisoslashuv, qishloq xo'jaligi mahsulotlari ishlab chiqarishi, infratuzilma, O'zbekiston.

Аннотация. В данной статье проанализированы объёмы и структура производства сельскохозяйственной продукции, а также роль региональной специализации в обеспечении продовольственной безопасности. В исследовании использованы методология ФАО и статистические данные за 2023 год. Полученные результаты позволили определить ключевые показатели продовольственной безопасности и оценить эффективность региональной специализации. Анализ показал, что регионы Ферганской долины специализируются на производстве плодоовощной продукции, тогда как южные регионы обладают высоким потенциалом в развитии животноводства и кормопроизводства. Корреляционный ($r = 0,78$) и регрессионный ($R^2 = 0,61$) анализы подтвердили наличие сильной положительной связи между уровнем развития инфраструктуры и обеспечением продовольственной безопасности. Результаты исследования свидетельствуют о том, что дальнейшее совершенствование систем хранения, логистики и сельскохозяйственной инфраструктуры будет способствовать укреплению региональной продовольственной безопасности и устойчивому развитию аграрного сектора.

Ключевые слова: продовольственная безопасность, региональная специализация, производство сельскохозяйственной продукции, инфраструктура, Узбекистан.

INTRODUCTION

The concept of food security was first officially defined at the United Nations World Food Conference held in 1974. Initially, the concept focused primarily on the supply side, emphasizing the availability of sufficient quantities of food and grain products. In 1983, the Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO) expanded the concept by incorporating the dimensions of physical and economic access to food. Later, at the World Food Summit in 1996, the widely accepted four-dimensional framework of food security was adopted, consisting of availability, access, utilization, and stability.

Modern approaches to food security consider its implementation at national, regional, household, and individual levels. At the national level, food security is associated with the balance between food supply and demand. At the regional level, it reflects the distribution of food resources among territories. At the household level, it concerns the adequacy of food provision for families, while at the individual level, it focuses on the quantity and quality of food consumption. Within this hierarchical system, agricultural production plays a fundamental role as the primary source for ensuring food security at all levels.

In the Republic of Uzbekistan, food security has become one of the priority areas of state policy. Its legal foundation was strengthened through the adoption of the “Food Security Strategy of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030.” The strategy focuses on increasing domestic food production, reducing dependence on imports, and promoting the development of agricultural clusters. The successful implementation of these objectives is closely linked to the development of agricultural production and supporting infrastructure.

LITERATURE REVIEW

The theoretical, methodological, and institutional foundations of regional food markets have been widely studied by foreign scholars, including R. Barrenar, S. Boynets, O. Bukenya, R. Dennis, J. Davis, R. Capone, and S. Kim. Their studies have contributed significantly to understanding the functioning and development of regional food systems.

Researchers from the Commonwealth of Independent States, including S. B. Avdasheva, A. I. Altukhov, T. P. Burdukova, S. S. Vorokov, V. V. Zakshevskaya, and G. M. Zinchuk, have examined issues related to increasing purchasing power, strengthening cooperative relations, and developing integrated food markets.

In Uzbekistan, scholars such as B. Ruzmetov, Sh. H. Nazarov, M. A. Sodiqov, A. B. Nizomov, T. F. Egamberdiyev, and M. A. Qodirov have conducted extensive research on food consumption assessment, food security indicators, and mechanisms for improving food supply systems.

The reviewed studies provide a valuable scientific foundation for understanding regional food markets and food security. At the same time, they highlight opportunities for further research on improving the mechanisms of regional food market development and strengthening food security through regional specialization and infrastructure enhancement.

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

The research employed a combination of functional-structural, quantitative, systematic, and comparative analysis methods. In addition, statistical grouping, economic-mathematical modeling, questionnaire surveys, expert assessments, and hierarchical analysis methods were applied to ensure the reliability and comprehensiveness of the study.

ANALYSIS AND RESULTS

According to the FAO methodology, several key conditions should be met to ensure food security. First, daily per capita calorie consumption should range between 2,100 and 2,500 kcal. Second, food expenditures should preferably remain within 30–35 percent of the family budget. Third, at least 70–75 percent of basic food products should be supplied through domestic production. Fourth, food reserves should be sufficient to cover consumption needs for 60–90 days.

An assessment of these indicators in Uzbekistan demonstrates positive progress in strengthening food security and highlights significant opportunities for further improvement through the development of agricultural infrastructure and regional specialization. Enhancing storage facilities, logistics systems, and production capacities can contribute to achieving higher levels of food security and sustainable agricultural development (Table 1).

Table 1
Food Security Indicators in Uzbekistan (2023)

Food Security Indicator	Uzbekistan (2023)	CIS Average	World Average	Optimal Level
Daily calorie consumption (kcal/person)	2,680	2,890	2,960	≥ 2,500
Food expenditure share (%)	38.4	32.1	28.7	≤ 30%
Level of domestic food supply (%)	71.3	78.6	82.4	≥ 75%
Food reserves (days)	48	67	74	≥ 60
Gini coefficient (food-related inequality)	0.31	0.27	0.24	< 0.25
Food import share (%)	22.8	18.3	15.6	≤ 20%

As shown in Table 1, Uzbekistan has achieved positive results in several food security indicators, while also demonstrating significant opportunities for further improvement. In particular, the share of food expenditures in the family budget (38.4%) and the level of food reserves (48 days) indicate the importance of continuing efforts to strengthen food security. The further development of agricultural infrastructure, including storage facilities, processing enterprises, and logistics systems, can play a key role in enhancing these indicators.

The agricultural sector plays an important role in the national economy of Uzbekistan, accounting for 28.3% of GDP in 2023. Although the sector's share in GDP has undergone certain structural changes over the past decade, the absolute volume of agricultural production has shown steady growth. In 2023, the gross value of agricultural production reached 215.7 trillion soums, representing an increase of 67.8% compared to 2019.

Crop production accounted for 58.1% of total agricultural output, while livestock production represented 41.9%. Within crop production, vegetables and melons (32.4%), cereals (18.7%), fruits and grapes (17.3%), industrial crops (cotton and others) (16.8%), and potatoes (8.6%) constituted the largest shares. In livestock production, meat production accounted for 38.2%, poultry for 24.7%, milk and dairy products for 22.4%, sheep and goat farming for 10.3%, and other livestock products for 4.4%.

Although the share of dehqan (household) farms decreased slightly from 64.2% in 2019 to 61.7% in 2023, they continue to make a substantial contribution to agricultural production. Their role remains particularly significant in the production of meat, milk, eggs, vegetables, and fruits. At the same time, the share of commercial farms increased from 32.1% to 35.1%, reflecting the positive impact of state support programs and the expansion of production capacities (Table 2).

Table 2
Dynamics of Agricultural Production by Product Type

Product Type	2019 (billion soums)	2021 (billion soums)	2023 (billion soums)	Growth, 2019–2023 (%)	Export Share (%)
Cereals and cereal products	21,450	28,100	36,800	71.6	2.3
Vegetables and melons	38,200	51,600	65,400	71.2	8.7
Fruits and grapes	22,800	30,400	41,200	80.7	15.4
Cotton	18,100	23,800	29,100	60.8	42.6
Potatoes and root crops	9,800	12,300	14,900	52.0	1.8
Beef and mutton	24,600	32,800	43,500	76.8	4.2
Poultry and eggs	15,300	20,100	27,200	77.8	3.1
Milk and dairy products	14,200	18,900	25,400	78.9	1.6
Fish and aquatic products	4,050	5,700	7,900	95.1	6.3
Total	168,500	223,700	291,400	73.0	–

The highest growth rates during 2019–2023 were recorded in the fisheries sector (95.1%), fruit and grape production (80.7%), and livestock farming. These results reflect the positive impact of intensive technologies, modernization processes, and state support programs implemented in these sectors. At the same time, the

high export shares of cotton (42.6%) and fruits and grapes (15.4%) indicate the continuing importance of specialization within Uzbekistan's agricultural sector.

Regional specialization is one of the central concepts of economic geography. It refers to the concentration of production and economic activities in a particular region based on its natural resources, economic potential, and comparative advantages. The classical theories of A. Smith, D. Ricardo, and J. S. Mill, particularly the theory of comparative advantage, provide the theoretical foundation for regional specialization. In modern economic geography, the concepts developed by P. Krugman, M. Porter's cluster theory, and J. Jacobs' agglomeration theory explain the contemporary mechanisms and effects of regional specialization.

A number of statistical indicators are used to measure regional specialization in the agricultural sector of Uzbekistan. One of the most widely applied indicators is the Specialization Coefficient (SC), which measures the share of a particular product in a region relative to its share at the national level:

$$SC = (q_{ih} / q_h) / (q_i / q)$$

where:

q_{ih} – production volume of product i in region h ;

q_h – total agricultural production volume in region h ;

q_i – national production volume of product i ;

q – total national agricultural production volume.

If $SC > 1$, the region is considered specialized in the production of that particular product.

The Localization Coefficient (LC) is also used as an additional indicator to assess the strength and stability of regional specialization. Furthermore, the Herfindahl–Hirschman Index (HHI) is widely applied to evaluate the degree of concentration and diversification within regional production structures. Together, these indicators provide a comprehensive assessment of regional specialization patterns in agriculture (Table 3).

Table 3
Regional Agricultural Specialization Coefficients (2023)

Region	Vegetables & Melons (SC)	Fruits & Grapes (SC)	Cereals (SC)	Cotton (SC)	Livestock (SC)	Main Specialization
Tashkent Region	1.42	1.18	0.87	0.64	1.05	Vegetables, Horticulture
Fergana Region	1.35	1.31	0.79	0.82	1.12	Vegetables, Horticulture
Andijan Region	1.29	1.24	0.83	0.71	1.08	Vegetables, Horticulture
Namangan Region	1.18	1.43	0.72	0.68	1.03	Viticulture, Horticulture
Samarkand Region	1.22	1.38	0.91	0.74	0.98	Viticulture, Vegetables
Kashkadarya Region	0.84	0.78	1.12	1.58	1.14	Cotton, Cereals
Surkhandarya Region	0.91	0.84	1.08	1.47	1.22	Cotton, Livestock
Khorezm Region	0.96	0.72	1.18	1.31	1.09	Cereals, Cotton
Navoi Region	0.74	0.68	1.22	1.24	1.18	Cereals, Livestock
Bukhara Region	0.82	0.76	1.16	1.35	1.21	Cotton, Cereals
Jizzakh Region	0.88	0.71	1.28	1.18	1.27	Cereals, Livestock
Syrdarya Region	0.94	0.68	1.31	1.42	1.04	Cereals, Cotton
Karakalpakstan	0.76	0.64	1.24	0.88	1.32	Livestock, Cereals

As can be seen from the specialization coefficient analysis, the regions of the Fergana Valley (Fergana, Andijan, and Namangan) demonstrate a strong specialization in vegetable, fruit, and grape production. In contrast, the southern and central regions, including Kashkadarya, Navoi, and Bukhara, are characterized by their specialization in cereal cultivation, cotton production, and livestock farming. These findings highlight the importance of aligning agricultural infrastructure development with the specific production profiles of each region, as infrastructure requirements differ according to the type of specialization.

In regions specialized in vegetables and melons, the development of storage facilities, refrigeration systems, and efficient logistics networks is particularly important. In cotton-producing regions, primary processing facilities and stronger integration with the textile industry can further enhance value creation. In grain-producing areas, the expansion of grain silos, warehouses, and flour-processing enterprises contributes to greater production efficiency and food security. Likewise, in livestock-specialized regions, the development of feed production facilities, veterinary services, and livestock support infrastructure plays a significant role in improving productivity and sustainability.

The main factors influencing food security can be classified into natural-climatic and socio-economic groups. Natural-climatic factors include soil fertility, climatic conditions, annual precipitation levels, average seasonal temperatures, and the availability of water resources for irrigation. Socio-economic factors include population density and composition, the level of economic activity, infrastructure development, the investment climate, and access to domestic and international markets.

The effective combination of these factors creates favorable conditions for sustainable agricultural development and contributes to strengthening regional and national food security.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

The results of the correlation analysis indicate a strong positive relationship between the level of infrastructure development and the regional food security index ($r = 0.78$). This finding demonstrates that regions with more developed agricultural and logistics infrastructure tend to achieve higher levels of food security. The statistical results therefore confirm the research hypothesis that infrastructure development is one of the key factors contributing to the strengthening of food security.

According to the regression analysis, the level of infrastructure development explains approximately 61% of the variation in the food security index ($R^2 = 0.61$). This result highlights the substantial contribution of infrastructure to food security outcomes. At the same time, other factors also play an important role, including household income levels (18%), the development of transport and communication systems (12%), and government support measures and subsidies (9%).

Overall, the findings suggest that continued investment in agricultural infrastructure, transportation networks, storage facilities, and regional specialization can further enhance food security and support sustainable agricultural development in Uzbekistan.

REFERENCES

1. Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan No. PF-5853 dated October 23, 2019, "On Approval of the Strategy for the Development of Agriculture of the Republic of Uzbekistan for 2020–2030." Available at: <https://lex.uz/docs/4567334>
2. Bukenya, J. O. (2020). Market Integration in the Staple Food Derivatives Markets in Uganda. *Journal of Food Distribution Research*, 51(1), 7–16.
3. Nazarov, Sh. H. (2016). Improving the Methodological Foundations for Enhancing the Competitiveness of Regions of Uzbekistan. Abstract of the Dissertation for the Degree of Doctor of Economic Sciences. Tashkent: Tashkent State University of Economics, 93 p.
4. World Food Crisis: A Serious Challenge of the Early 21st Century. Available at: <https://institutions.com/general/1142-mirovoj-prodovolstvennyj-krizis.html>
5. Food and Agriculture Organization (FAO). Presentation of the State of Food Security and Nutrition in the World. Available at: <https://www.fao.org/europe/events/detail-events/en/c/1298531/>
6. Bekmurodov, N. Kh. (2026). A Comprehensive Methodology for Assessing the Development and Efficiency of Agricultural Production Infrastructure at the Regional Level. *American Journal of Economics and Business Management*, 9(5), 729–737.

IQTISODIYOT & TARAQQIYOT

Ijtimoiy, iqtisodiy, texnologik, ilmiy, ommabop jurnal

Ingliz tili muharriri: Feruz HAKIMOV

Musahhih: Zokir ALIBEKOV

Sahifalovchi va dizayner: Hasan MAQSUDOV

2026. № 6/3

© Materiallar ko'chirib bosilganda "Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali manba sifatida ko'rsatilishi shart. Jurnalda bosilgan material va reklamalardagi dalillarning aniqligiga mualliflar ma'sul. Tahririyat fikri har vaqt ham mualliflar fikriga mos kelmasligi mumkin. Tahririyatga yuborilgan materiallar qaytarilmaydi.

Mazkur jurnalda maqolalar chop etish uchun quyidagi havolalarga maqola, reklama, hikoya va boshqa ijodiy materiallar yuborishingiz mumkin. Materiallar va reklamalar pullik asosda chop etiladi.

EI.Pochta: sq143235@gmail.com

Bot: @iqtisodiyot_77

Tel.: 93 718 40 07

Jurnalga istalgan payt quyidagi rekvizitlar orqali obuna bo'lishingiz mumkin. Obuna bo'lgach, @iqtisodiyot_77 telegram sahifamizga to'lov haqidagi ma'lumotni skrinshot yoki foto shaklida jo'natishingizni so'raymiz. Shu asosda har oygi jurnal yangi sonini manzilingizga jo'natamiz.

"Yashil" iqtisodiyot va taraqqiyot" jurnali 03.11.2022-yildan O'zbekiston Respublikasi Prezidenti Adminstratsiyasi huzuridagi Axborot va ommaviy kommunikatsiyalar agentligi tomonidan №566955 reyestr raqami tartibi bo'yicha ro'yxatdan o'tkazilgan.

Litsenziya raqami: №046523. PNFL: 30407832680027

Manzilimiz: Toshkent shahar, Mirzo Ulug'bek tumani
Kumushkon ko'chasi, 26-uy.

Jurnal sayti: <https://yashil-iqtisodiyot-taraqqiyot.uz>